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ИНТЕЛЛИГЕНТНОСТЬ КАК ПОСТУЛАТ ДОБРОТЫ И ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ (ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЙ ПРИМЕР ЗНАЧЕНИЯ)

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются основные понятия о толерантности и доброте, их пропаганда среди интеллигенции общества. Также охарактеризована интерпретация интеллигенции в российском, европейском и среднеазиатском обществе. Идеи известных представителей интеллигенции характеризуют её как чувство сельской интеллигентности, осознание прогресса, нравственных норм, социальной ответственности перед народом. В статье анализируются самооценка перфекционизма ума, целей, саморазвития, культурного прогресса, толерантности, доброты и расширения кругозора само по себе, также выход из изоляции интеллигенции от народа, являются основными вопросами работы

Ключевые слова: интеллигенты, интеллектуалы, интеллигенция, интеллигентное общество, учитель(устоз), местная интеллигенция, культура(цивильность)

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ZIYOLILIK MEHRIBONLIK VA OLIYJANOBLIK SIYMOSI SIFATIDA(MA'NONING AMALIY TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada bag'rikenglik va mehr-oqibat, ularni jamiyat ziyolilari o'rtasida targ'ib qilish haqidagi asosiy tushunchalar muhokama qilindi. Rossiya, Yevropa va Markaziy Osiyo jamiyatida ziyolilarning talqini ham tavsiflangan. Mashhur ziyolilar g'oyalari uni qishloq ziyoliligi, taraqqiyotni anglash, axloqiy me'yorlar, xalq oldidagi ijtimoiy mas'uliyat hissi sifatida tavsiflaydi. Maqolada ong, maqsadlar, o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish, madaniy taraqqiyot, bag'rikenglik, mehribonlik va ufqning kengayishi kabi o'zini o'zi qadrlash tahlil qilinadi. Fidoyilik, yaxshilikka xizmat qilish, butun insoniyatga xizmat qilishga samimiy tayyorlik, beqarorlik, ijtimoiy mavqening ishonchsizligi. o'z-o'zidan ziyolilarni xalqdan ajratib qo'yishdan qutulish ishning asosiy masalalaridir.

Kalit so'zlar: ziyolilar, zukkolar, ziyolilik, ziyoli qatlam, ustoz, mahalliy ziyolilar, madaniyatlilik

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INTELLIGENCE AS THE KINDNESS AND TOLERANCE POSTULATE (THE INTERPRETATION OF MEANING IN PRACTICE)

ABSTRACT

The main concept about tolerance and kindness, their propaganda among intellectuals society has discussed in the article. The interpretation of intelligentsia in Russian, European and Central Asian society has been characterized, as well. The ideas of famous representatives of intelligentsia characterize it as the sense of rural intelligence, awareness of progress, moral norms, social responsibility toward the people. The self-esteem of perfectionism of mind, purposes, self-development, cultural progress, tolerance, kindness and broadening horizon are analyzed in the article. Ideas of sacrifice, service good, sincere readiness to serve all mankind, precariousness, unreliability of social position in itself, escaping the isolation of the intelligentsia from the people are the main questions of the work.

Key words. Intelligence, intellectuals, intelligentsia, intelligentsia community, uztoz, rural intellectuals, civility

Introduction. Point of view takes into account other works about intelligence and intelligentsia is completed [How intelligentsia lives, 2018; Dakoro (a), 2014; Dakoro, 2014 (b)], which raises the problem of defining and distinguishing between intelligentsia and intellectuals [Usmanov, 2016; Golubeva, 2011].

According to M. Dakoro, "the meaning of the term ("intelligentsia" is E.Z.) has always been rather vague and debatable, and this trend keeps its actuality until today. The vagueness of the term ...is clarified by keeping imbalance of the social position that the intelligentsia has occupied Uzbek society for a long time, uncertainty its social status, as well as some mismatch between high self-esteem of the intelligentsia and its real position", "starting from the 19th century, quite an intense controversy was conducted around the intelligentsia, which took place mainly in the community of the intelligentsia itself.

Hypothesis. INTELLIGENTSIA, based on a word of Latin origin meaning intelligence, has come into the modern global vocabulary from Russia. By the 1870s the word identified a particular type of publicly active Russian intellectual. The concept of "intelligentsia" arose, as is commonly believed, in 1866, introduced it by P.D. Boborykin. However, modern researchers note that the term intelligentsia was used before - in 1863 it is found in I.S. Aksakov, and in the diary of V.A. Zhukovsky, it was founded in his dairy in 1836. Thus, the word arose earlier than it was implemented as the concept into the field of wide public attention "

There is a professional (a stratum of society with special knowledge in the field of culture, education, science and technology, knowledge workers) and an ideological understanding of the intelligentsia. M. Gasparov adheres to a mixed understanding. He believes that the border between the people and the intelligentsia "lies on the level of education", but argues that the intelligentsia, "according to the common European understanding, is a layer of society brought up to lead society, but has not found vacancies for this and offers society its criticism or their proposals from outside" [Gasparov, 2001].

Uzbek interpretation of intelligentsia has its own meaning as "Engaged in intellectual work; knowledgeable, educated, enlightened.

Intellectuals are a layer engaged in various complex types of mental work (science and culture workers, teachers, engineers, technicians, doctors).

A dilettante is a person who expresses an opinion about everything in the world without having sufficient knowledge. Dilettantism is a sign of lack of culture and has nothing to do with true culture and intelligence.

◆ Rural intellectuals. Congratulatory words are being heard from the pulpits in honor of the people's intellectuals. From the newspaper.

◆ Engineers are also intelligent considered an intelligentsia? Yakubjon said looking at Saidi. A. Kakhdar, "Mirage". [p. explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language .letter Z. p.148].

Intellectuality means being the owner of mental perfection, being ready to understand theoretical issues and mastering scientific knowledge. If "intelligentsia" means a highly developed intelligent, widely educated, highly cultured, "intellectual" means a social stratum among the classes of people, which is engaged in highly skilled mental work.

Intellectuals are a layer engaged in various complex types of mental work (science and culture workers, teachers, engineers, technicians, doctors).

Civility means having human qualities such as humility, honesty, truthfulness, generosity, humanity, kindness, generosity, full adherence to moral rules, and respect for one's own nation and other peoples.

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Method. Developing a sense of intelligence (ziyolilik)in a person is the focus of the life . D.S. Likhachev said that the more intelligent a person is, the more he understands and assimilates, the wider his worldview and scope of acceptance. The narrower a person's cultural level is, the more indifferent he is to all news and "too old". He lives with his old habits. He has a narrow worldview and is suspicious of everything. Knowing the cultural values of the past and the cultures of other nations, preserving and increasing them, developing the ability to accept their aesthetic value is considered one of the most important means of cultural development. The history of the development of human culture is not only the history of the search for new, but also old cultural values. Also, knowledge of other cultures, in a certain sense, is combined with the history of humanism. This means respect for other peoples, tolerance in the right sense, wish for peace [Likhachyov D. S. Poetika drevnerusskoy literaturi. M.Science . 1979, p.159.]

The opinion of N. Berdyaev is known, who believes that “Western people would fall into a mistake identifying the intelligentsia with what the West calls intellectuals. Intellectuals are people of intellectual labor and creativity, primarily scientists, writers, artists, professors, teachers, etc.” [Berdyaev, 1990: 17].

Discussing intelligentsia, scientists name among its properties “high moral responsibility, orientation towards the interests of the people, the desire to personify samples of professional culture, to be an example both in public (public) and in private (private) life”, “ideas of sacrifice, service good”, sincere readiness to serve all mankind, precariousness, unreliability of social position in itself”, “the isolation of the intelligentsia from the people, who they served and for whose freedom they fought”, “tolerance in the “national question”, intellectuals are perceived as “renegades for society. [Yu. Lotman]

Education is the main sign of intelligence, and its general cultural level is often reflected in speech culture. Cultural speech means correct speech first of all. A cultured person expresses his opinion through figurative, expressive and beautiful speech.

An intellectual has a high esthetic taste, that is, not only to think about the beauty of works of art, but also to think about the beauty of people, nature and society, to resist rudeness and injustice and eliminate it. will be able to. A sense of moderation and harmony in everything is a high quality of intelligence.

Results. Representatives of Central Asian intellectuals as Chingiz Aytmatov , Muchtal Avezov and Sadridin Ayni enlightened the intelligence .Chingiz Aitmatov, along with the great Kazakh writer Abai Kunanbaev, considered Sadridin Aini, the Hero of Uzbekistan, the founder of modern Tajik literature, his master (ustaz), spiritual mentor. Although Chingiz Aitmatov was not personally acquainted with his spiritual ustad - Sadridin Aini. But, a couple of years later, when Chingiz entered the M. Gorky Literary Institute, there was a good opportunity to get acquainted with

the great sons of the Tajik people who worked in Moscow: academician Bobojon Gafurov, young scientist Akbar Tursunov, who later became an academician of the Academy of Sciences of Tajikistan, and often visited in the capital of the USSR, Moscow, by the poet Mirzo Tursunzade - Chairman of the Solidarity Committee of Asian and African countries, a member of the Soviet Committee for the Defense of Peace, the All-Union Committee for the Lenin and State Prizes of the USSR in the field of literature, art and architecture under the Council of Ministers of the USSR.[find it: <http://tursunzoda.tj/2019/10/18/pust-druzhboj-budet-polon-mir-obrashhenie/>]

Discussion and conclusion. The successors of the holy work of these great people are trying to restore those lost relationship. Tolerance and kindness. It can be given a number of examples when public figure, the representatives of intelligentsia, who do a lot in strengthening the friendship of peoples, peace and solidarity. His motto is: LET THE WORLD BE FULL OF FRIENDSHIP! As a result of fruitful literary translation activity, I met with writers who always reciprocate those who sincerely love him and are faithful to our Asian tradition and mutual respect. Our creative etiquette allows us to help in the work of strengthening literary ties between our peoples.

Poets, prose writers and translators of both countries see and notice more than others, think deeper and speak wiser than others, they want to bring their humane values and ideals to people. That's the power of creative people! Poetry should be an echo of time, reflect all the events taking place in the world, and first of all, the Homeland and the lives of contemporaries. It was not connected with financial interest of countries or memorandum for any benefit. It was propaganda of kindness.

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